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The human breast during early transformation.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

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2 **Results**

3 The human breast during early transformation.

4 GSE72205.

5 Changes in tolerance: the ability to distinguish self from non self at the cell surface in human tissues.

6 Evidence of host activation of defense responses and tumor but whether the responses were protective or
7 tumor promoting were not always discernable.

8 Ifna4

9 IFIT5 was silenced while IFI16 was activated. IFI6 and IFI35 did not change in expression. A modest
10 increase in IFITM3 was observed.

11 Natural killer activation marker NKG7 was induced, providing evidence that the host activates NK cell
12 recruitment in human DCIS to limit breast cancer and supporting the concept that a complex and
13 diametrically opposed conflict occurs in humans during early cancer, reflective of responses that are
14 strictly based on an evolutionary consideration, the desire of the host or the tumor to survive. Cancer
15 results in death when the host ultimately succumbs to organ failure resulting from metastasis which is a
16 direct function of an inability to maintain dominance in this conflict.

17 CCL16 and CCL20 suppression.

18 CXCR4 induction for tolerance/senescence

19 Il1f7

20 VDR induction.

21 FPR2 induction.

22 HAVCR2 was activated

23 IL17 modulation.

24 FEZF2 is a second transcription or nuclear factor, in addition to the autoimmune regulator AIRE that
25 functions in activation of tissue restricted antigen at the thymus. Its activation is associated with the ability
26 to tolerize lymphocytes to self by activation of TRA, whose presentation is used as a template to select
27 against auto reactive TCR in developing lymphocytes in the mTEC of the thymus (negative selection).
28 FEZF2 silencing was observed suggesting both that FEZF2 functioned at a presumed basal level to
establish a low level of tolerance in non hematopoietic tissues, and that FEZF2 silencing was thus a
compensatory host response that countered evasion of tumor defense of evidenced by changes in
cytokine secretion, modulation of multiple tolerance mechanisms like induction of VDR and exhaustion
receptors that function in tolerance responses like HAVCR2 (Tim-3).

We found evidence of the involvement of Rhesus factors in tumor defense assessed by silencing or
reduction of Rhesus factors RHCE and RHCG, suggesting that the established relationship of Rh family
genes with histocompatibility or reactivity in the blood was associated with, related to or a function of Rh
family genes together with Ly antigens at the surface to establish homeostatic self non self responses, and
alter this threshold to execute effective anti tumor responses by changing Rh antigen expression as the
surface of the tumor to signal the presence of non-self (arguing against reduction of Rh family antigen in
the tumor during DCIS as a tumor response that indicated an alternative function for Rh antigens,
functioning in recruitment of appropriate immune cells for clearance, rather than the opposite which we
propose, that Rh factor expression occurs in the tissues, imparts a tolerogenic force or presence at the cell
surface, and can be silenced by the host to modulated the threshold in the presence of non self.

GYPE and GYPB were silenced.

1 Other activity we observed during early cancer or pre cancer was a pattern of changes in complement
2 pathway and platelet clotting cascade gene expression that described the presence of an alternative anti
3 tumor response mechanism involving induction of specific complement and clotting genes. These
4 included Induction of C1QTNF6 and F13A1.

5 FCRLA, FCGR1B and FCGR3B were silenced.

6 Immune receptors LILRA4 and NCF2 were also silenced. Expression of immunoglobulini-like Siglec12 and
7 SIGIRR was also ablated suggested of silencing by the tumor.

8 The extracellular matrix in early cancer (DCIS) in the human breast.

9 MME13, MMP11, MMP8, MMP9 and MMP28 were early changes

10 GYG2 and Nlgn4x change indicating Xist imprinting had already occurred and suggesting its importance
11 on the actual process
12 Dazap1 was activated.

13 ATRX was silenced, as was a collection of RAD family genes including Rad50, Rad17, Rad51, Rad51C,
14 and Rad54L.

15 ECT2, DUX family, and transformation: ECT2 induction relative to the transformation from normal breast,
16 DCIS to ODC, and determining the kinetics of DUX family modulation during transformation and
17 progression to carcinoma

18 ECT2 expression was not measured or available but the DUX factors were expressed early and late

19 Cell death: CIDEA was silenced, MLKL and ROPK5. IAP-family BAIAP2 was induced.

20 BAI1, a brain specific angiogenesis inhibitor was activated, supporting the concept that from the point of
21 CDKN induction during the initial senescent block prior to the first cell division, a continued host cell
22 autonomous anti tumor response was present (cell death activation as compared to immune-mediated
23 recruitment and clearance responses).

24 Growth factor and morphogen changes

25 FAP activation was observed in DCIS, together with induction of VEGF-A and PDGF-B. TdGF and gdnf
26 expression was silenced, or had already decreased from an assumed prior activation. VGF was
27 expressed at this time. BMP10 was activated in humans during DCIS, as was Wnt2B and Wnt5B. FGF22
28 activation together with FGFR4 enrichment was observed. IGFBP5, IGFBP6, and IGFBP7 were each
29 expressed at relatively higher levels in human DCIS.

30 Continued evasion of cell survival restriction through signaling at the cell surface.

31 We found activation of AXL in the transformed tissues of humans with DCIS, together with induction of
32 pathway ligands GAS7 and GAS2L3. GAS7 signaling through AXL is likely important during the transition
33 to stage I cancer from DCIS in humans, an example of a mechanism that maintains dominance of the
34 tumor in a composite outcome of a collection of opposite, compensatory (largely binary) decisions by the
35 host and the tumor.

36 Activation of kinase ALK was also observed in situ. ITK an FYN were highly expressed, as were TEK and
37 BLK to a less significant level, but LCK, LYN, SRC and BTK were not. MAPK1, MAPK7, and MAPK10
38 were all activated in situ. PPP1R1B and PPP2R1A were activated, as were PTPRO and PTP4A3.

1 IKZF family genes are activated and repressed from the breast to the primary tumor, the lymph nodes and
2 the brain. Their transcriptional activation and repression had occurred during in situ ductal carcinoma
3 (early cancer): IKZF3 was activated while IKZF2 was silenced. A second change in nuclear factor
expression observed, with a switch on Neurod2 and Neurod6 expression.

4 Hoxb5, HOXC6, and HOXC10 were activated, together with LHX9 and TSHZ3. Other nuclear factors were
5 silenced or induced. KLF16 and KLF10 were activated. SOX18 and SOX13 were induced in the breast
6 during transformation in situ. ROR2 induction was observed, as was BCL11B. TBX1 and TBX10 were
7 activated in situ, as were TCF3 and TCF7L1. PAX6 was highly activated, with expression of PAX8 in
ductal carcinoma in situ. RUNX1 activation was also observed, as was high activation of PBX4 and TGIF1.
DLX4 and DLX5 were modestly expressed in situ. GATA4 and GATA6 were silenced. The data suggested
acquisition of identity for the tumor, molecular subtype selection, was an extended process and not a
product of evolution within a founder clone or founder clone population of limited number.

8 CHD3 was silenced while MBD2 was activated. BRD3 was activated, and MLLT3 was silenced. HDAC7A
9 was activated during DCIS.

10 Drug resistance ATP-binding cassette MDR genes were activated. ABCA7, ABCD4, ABCA2, ABCG4,
11 ABCC5 and ABCC2 were all enriched in the breast early during transformation. SLC46A1 and SLC47A3,
genes of the SLC family with described relation to the ABC transporters was observed in situ.

12 EMT is important for metastasis. The time at which progression to disseminated disease occurs is argued
13 to occur both early in disease, or later once the tumor has reached a size that is sufficient for cells to
detach from active change at the ECM on the tumor surface (or mechanical detachment due to breach).
Twist and Snail family genes are the major regulators of EMT. We observed ealdry silencing of SNAI2 that
14 was more likely indicative of an indication of organized subsequent to changes in EMT program that occur
early during transformation. Other evidence of an EMT program that functioned in DCIS after
15 transformation of the founder clones but prior to emergence of advanced disease was activation of
COL1A1 and COL1A2 and increased vimentin expression. Zyxin was activated; E- and N-cadherin
16 activation was not present but CDH11 was activated together with multiple protocadherin including
PCDHA10 and PCDHA17.

17 Expression of BEX4, CLDN9, TM7SF4, and BCAS3 and FAM78A during DCIS suggested their ability to
18 mark tissues undergoing malignant activity (transformation). We recently presented a more
comprehensive panel of markers for use in detection of cancer in the human breast. Many of the genes
19 expressed in the established tumor signature were detectable and highly enriched here, in situ, suggesting
their ability to identify early changes in disease.